

1

1 **Prenatal exposure estimation of BPA and DEHP using integrated external and internal**
2 **dosimetry: A case study**

3

4 M. A. Martínez^a, J. Rovira^{a,b}, R. Prasad Sharma^a, M. Nadal^b, M. Schuhmacher^{a,b}, V. Kumar^{a,b}

5

6 *^aEnvironmental Engineering Laboratory, Departament d'Enginyeria Química, Universitat*
7 *Rovira i Virgili, Av. Països Catalans 26, 43007 Tarragona, Catalonia, Spain.*

8 *^bLaboratory of Toxicology and Environmental Health, School of Medicine, IISPV,*
9 *Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Sant Llorenç 21, 43201 Reus, Catalonia, Spain.*

10

11

12

13

14

15

16

17

18

19

20

21

22

23

24

25 * Corresponding author: Vikas Kumar

26 E-mail: vikas.kumar@urv.cat

27 Tel: +34 977 558576

2

3

28ABSTRACT

29Exposure to Endocrine disruptors (EDs), such as Bisphenol A (BPA) and di (2-ethylhexyl)
30phthalate (DEHP), has been associated with obesity and diabetes diseases in childhood, as well
31as reproductive, behavioral and neurodevelopment problems. The aim of this study was to
32estimate the prenatal exposure to BPA and DEHP through food consumption for pregnant
33women living in Tarragona County (Spain). Probabilistic calculations of prenatal exposure were
34estimated by integrated external and internal dosimetry modelling, physiologically based
35pharmacokinetic (PBPK) model, using a Monte-Carlo simulation. Physical characteristic data
36from the cohort, along with food intake information from the questionnaires (concentrations of
37BPA and DEHP in different food categories and the range of the different food ratios), were
38used to estimate the value of the total dietary intake for the Tarragona pregnancy cohort. The
39major contributors to the total dietary intake of BPA were canned fruits and vegetables,
40followed by canned meat and meat products. In turn, milk and dairy products, followed by
41ready to eat food (including canned dinners), were the most important contributors to the total
42dietary intake of DEHP. Despite the dietary variations among the participants, the intakes of
43both chemicals were considerably lower than their respective current tolerable daily intake
44(TDI) values established by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA). Internal dosimetry
45estimates suggest that the plasma concentrations of free BPA and the most important DEHP
46metabolite, mono (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (MEHP), in pregnant women were characterized by
47transient peaks (associated with meals) and short half-lives (<2 h). In contrast, fetal exposure
48was characterized by a low and sustained basal BPA and MEHP concentration due to a lack of
49metabolic activity in the fetus. Therefore, EDs may have a greater effect on developing organs
50in young children or in the unborn child.

51

52 **Keywords:** Endocrine disruptors; Bisphenol A (BPA); di (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP);
53 mono (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (MEHP); physiologically based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) model;
54 Prenatal exposure.

55

56 1. Introduction

57 The endocrine system secretes hormones which regulate the metabolic functions of the body.
58 Endocrine disruptors (EDs) are substances that can mimic or partly mimic naturally occurring
59 hormones in the body like estrogens, androgens, and thyroid hormones (Matsui, 2008). EDs can
60 also bind to a receptor within a cell and block the endogenous hormone from binding. (Sharma
61 et al., 2016 a). Therefore, EDs can interfere or block the way natural hormones or their receptors
62 are made or controlled (Thomson and Grounds, 2005). Bisphenol A (BPA) and di (2-
63 ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP), among others, are very important EDs due to the widespread
64 distribution of products that contain them. According to the World Health Organization (WHO),
65 both of these chemicals can cause adverse health effects in an intact organism, or its progeny
66 (Hughes et al., 2006; Meeker, 2012; WHO, 2012). The effects of prenatal and early exposures to
67 EDs may be manifested any time in life (Giulivo et al., 2016; Sharma et al., 2016 a).

68 Around 3 billion kilograms of BPA are produced annually worldwide and over 100,000
69 kilograms of this compound are released annually into the atmosphere (Myridakis et al., 2016).
70 BPA is used in industry for the production of resins and polycarbonate plastic. Although the use
71 of BPA in Europe is banned for the manufacture of plastic materials in contact with food
72 intended for children (0-3 years) (European-Parliament, 2011), it is not banned in polycarbonate
73 (PC) plastics for other uses. It can be found in food and beverage processing, and in many other
74 commercial products such as epoxy resin cans, dental sealants, personal care products, baby
75 bottles, building materials, flame retardant materials, optical lenses, materials for the protection
76 of window glazing, DVDs, and household electronics (Geens et al., 2012; Myridakis et al.,
77 2016). Although the ingestion of BPA from food or water is the predominant route of exposure
78 (Lorber et al., 2015), there are other nonfood routes, such as inhalation of free BPA
79 (concentrations in indoor and outdoor air), indirect ingestion (dust, soil, and toys), and dermal
80 route (contact with thermal papers and application of dental treatment), which contributes to the
81 total BPA exposure (Myridakis et al., 2016). In addition, recent studies (De Coensel et al., 2009;
82 Sungur et al., 2014) have seen that temperature has a major impact on the BPA migration level
83 into water; an increase from 40 °C to 60 °C can lead to a 6 - 10 fold increase in the migration

84level (De Coensel et al., 2009). The TDI of BPA is 4 µg/kg bw/day (EFSA, 2015). However,
85other studies have demonstrated that dosages below the current TDI could cause significant
86effects in animal models (Rezg et al., 2014). In the context of developmental risk, some authors
87affirm that BPA can affect the reproductive system and adipocyte differentiation (Myridakis et
88al., 2016). Especially for children, exposure to these EDs appears to be related to altered birth
89weight, male genital abnormalities, and behavioral and neurodevelopmental problems
90(Rochester, 2013; Tewar et al., 2016).

91 Phthalates are ubiquitous environmental contaminants made up of dialkylesters or alkyl and
92aryl esters of orthophthalic acid (1,2-dicarboxylic acid). High-molecular-weight phthalates
93(HMWP) can be found in tubing, vinyl flooring, and wall covering (Mallozzi et al., 2016). Low-
94molecular-weight phthalates (LMWP) more commonly can be present in personal care products
95(shampoo, cosmetics, fragrances and nail polish) (Mallozzi et al., 2016). Phthalates are also
96found as both inert and active ingredients in some pesticide formulations (EFSA, 2015). It is
97known that food is the major source of exposure to diisobutyl (DiBP), di-n-butyl (DnBP), and di
98(2-ethylhexyl) (DEHP) phthalate (Wormuth et al., 2006). However, other sources such as
99dermal contact with products that contain them, dust ingestion and inhalation, are also potential
100contributors to human exposure (Arbuckle et al., 2016). An additional exposure route for young
101children is through mouthing toys, childcare articles and other products containing phthalates.
102Through mouthing of these products, phthalates can dissolve in saliva and finally be absorbed
103into the bloodstream. (De Coensel et al., 2009). Once absorbed, phthalate diesters are quickly
104metabolized into monoesters (as MEHP), which are biologically active and ultimately excreted
105in urine (Genuis et al., 2012). DEHP metabolite, the mono (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (MEHP), is
106the most toxic and active one among these phthalates (Gobas et al., 2016). The EFSA and the
107European Chemical agency (ECHA) established a TDI of 50 µg/kg bw/day for DEHP (EFSA,
1082015; ECHA, 2010). In the context of risk, DEHP and its metabolite MEHP, mainly affect
109estrogen production and action in granulosa cells, resulting in hypo-estrogenic, polycystic ovary
110and anovulatory cycles. This leads to infertility and affects the reproductive development of the
111fetus (Das et al., 2014; Davis et al., 1994; Lovekamp-Swan and Davis, 2003; Wang et al., 2015).

112 BPA and phthalates are considered “non-persistent” EDs because they are rapidly eliminated
113 from the human body. Despite their short biological half-lives, exposure is prevalent and
114 continuous because of their widespread use in food and everyday products, leading to consistent
115 detection of these EDs in human biological matrices like urine and blood. BPA undergoes
116 glucuronidation and sulfation producing BPAG and BPAS in the liver, respectively (Hanioka et
117 al., 2008; Kim et al., 2003). These metabolites are not toxic in comparison to BPA (Gramec
118 Skledar and Peterlin Mašič, 2016). Instead, DEHP is metabolized into mono (2-ethylhexyl)
119 phthalate (MEHP), which is more toxic than DEHP (Gobas et al., 2016; Latini, 2005).

120 Optimal development and health in early life are key factors for health and wellbeing during
121 later childhood and adulthood. It has been hypothesized that adult health and disease have their
122 origin in the prenatal and early postnatal environment, a concept referred to as the
123 Developmental Origins of Health and Disease (Hanson and Gluckman, 2011). There are various
124 parameters early in life, which are indicators for development later in life. The exposition to
125 these EDs in the early period of life conditions to suffer and develop illnesses like obesity and
126 type 2 diabetes in childhood and adulthood (Casas et al., 2011; De Cock et al., 2014; Myridakis
127 et al., 2016).

128 The aim of this study is to estimate the prenatal exposure to EDs (BPA and DEHP) through
129 the dietary intake of pregnant women using integrated external and internal dosimetry
130 estimation. To assess the prenatal exposure, we used a mathematical physiologically based
131 pharmacokinetic model (PBPK) adapted for pregnancy, in order to know the internal dosimetry
132 levels of EDs in the fetus. PBPK models are mathematical representations of the human body
133 aimed at describing the time course distribution of chemicals in human tissues (Fàbrega et al.,
134 2016). In recent years, PBPK models have been used in human health risk assessment to
135 estimate the burdens of chemicals in human tissues, thus avoiding the analysis of this kind of
136 samples (Fàbrega et al., 2014; Fàbrega et al., 2015; Schuhmacher et al., 2014). The present
137 study is in the framework of the “HEALS” project (FP7-603946), Health and environmental-
138 wide associations based on large population surveys.

139

140 2. Materials and Methods

141 2.1 Study Population cohort

142 The study population comprises a cohort of pregnant women and ongoing birth cohort. The
143 pregnant women were recruited during the first trimester of pregnancy as part of the European
144 “HEALS” project. The recruitment of pregnant mothers has started in March 2016 and in the
145 present study 45 mother-child pairs were included. Women were informed of the study during
146 their first prenatal visit to the University Hospital “Sant Joan de Reus”, in Reus, Catalonia,
147 Spain. Women were eligible to participate according to the following inclusion criteria: ≥ 16
148 years, intention to deliver at the reference hospital, and no problems with the communication
149 language. This study was approved by the Ethical Committee of Clinical Research of the
150 University Hospital “Sant Joan de Reus”. Written informed consent was obtained from the
151 participants.

152

153 2.2 Pregnancy and diet

154 Diet has been considered the primary source of BPA and phthalates exposure (Lakind and
155 Naiman, 2010; Maffini et al., 2006; Welshons et al., 2006). Therefore, face-to-face food
156 frequency questionnaires (FFQ) and personal interviews were used in order to determine the
157 pregnant women’s dietary intake of BPA and DEHP, like other authors had done it before
158 (Casas et al., 2011; Myridakis et al., 2016). Apart from food frequency questions, the
159 questionnaires also included a set of questions targeting to know other sources of these
160 compounds.

161 Dietary factors were assessed using FFQ (times per week), the questionnaires give
162 information about general food intakes by mothers during pregnancy trimesters. These
163 questionnaires were originally designed to assess average dietary intakes during two phases of
164 pregnancy: the 1st FFQ covered the year before pregnancy and the 2nd FFQ covered the whole
165 pregnancy including the last period until birth. Intake frequency for each food item was

166 converted to an average daily intake for each participant and then expressed like servings/week.
 167 Different food items from the FFQs administered during pregnancy study were classified in 8
 168 general food groups: a) Grains and grain-based products (cereals, pasta, and bread), b) Milk and
 169 dairy products (milk, yogurt, hard cheese and fresh cheese), c) Meat and meat products
 170 (chicken, turkey, beef, pork, lamb and minced meat), d) Fish and other seafood (white fish, blue
 171 fish and seafood), e) Fruits and vegetables (salad, green beans, swiss chard, spinach, garnish
 172 vegetables, potatoes, and), f) Legumes (lentils, chickpeas, and white beans), g) Ready to eat
 173 (pre-cooked and canned food) and h) Water. In addition, questions potentially relevant to EDs
 174 exposure were asked: type and frequency of water consumption (bottled water or tap water),
 175 organic food consumption, heating and use of plastic microwave food containers and
 176 consumption of plastic packaged food or canned food. Especially canned food is considered as
 177 the predominant source of BPA and DEHP (Hartle et al., 2016; Schecter et al., 2013).

178 Face-to-face interviews were conducted with mothers during pregnancy about habits and
 179 lifestyle, in order to know relevant information related to the exposure to EDs, such as smoking
 180 or alcohol drinking, hobbies or activities that they usually do, place of living and work
 181 environment.

182

183 2.3 BPA and DEHP total dietary intake assessment

184 The estimation of the total dietary intake of BPA and DEHP for pregnant women was
 185 calculated according to equation A.1.

186

$$187 \quad \text{Total dietary intake} = (C_{\text{BPA/DEHP}} \cdot F_r \cdot F_f) / \text{BW} / 7 \quad \text{Eq. (A.1)}$$

188 Where $C_{\text{BPA/DEHP}}$ is the BPA or DEHP concentration found in the different food categories (in
 189 $\mu\text{g/kg}$); F_r is the food ingestion ration (in kg/ration); F_f is the food frequency consumption (in
 190 ration/week), and BW is the body weight (in kg). The total dietary intake is given in $\mu\text{g/kg}$
 191 bw/day . Data used to assess the total dietary intake of BPA and DEHP is shown in Table 1.

192 Concentrations of BPA and DEHP in the different food categories were taken from the
193 literature with a preference rule of Spanish > Mediterranean > European average > other
194 available data. The range of the different food rations was taken from Spanish Society of
195 Community Nutrition (Serra Majem, 2011). Finally, the food frequency and body weight were
196 taken from the cohort of the present study. To deal with variability and uncertainty of
197 parameters mentioned, probabilistic estimation of the total dietary intake was performed using
198 Monte-Carlo simulation. Monte-Carlo simulation is a common approach used to incorporate
199 variability and uncertainty of the parameters mentioned into the estimation of human health
200 exposure (Mari et al., 2009; May et al., 2002; Rovira et al., 2016; Schuhmacher et al., 2001).
201 Table 1 includes the probabilistic distribution of parameters for the calculation of human health
202 exposure. In this study, Monte-Carlo simulation was carried out by Oracle Crystal Ball[®]. This
203 program is able to calculate risk based on the propagation variable of variability and uncertainty
204 given by each parameter probability function until a certain number of iterations. An iteration
205 size of 100,000 was used. Appropriate probabilistic distributions were used according to the
206 input parameters (concentrations of BPA and DEHP in the different food categories, food
207 fraction, food frequency, and body weight): Log-normal, triangular and uniform distribution
208 (Table 1). In general, we used triangular distribution when the literature data was limited; in
209 these cases, the minimum, maximum and mean values of the parameter were considered. We
210 used log-normal distributions only for positive values and when literature data was available
211 (mean and standard values). Finally, we used the uniform distribution when the information
212 available was only the min-max range assuming equal probability of occurrence. To simulate
213 different exposure scenarios, detailed data from the cohort study (food frequency and the body
214 weight of the mothers) has also been considered. A complementary aspect of the Monte-Carlo
215 study is the possibility of creating sensitivity charts, which show information about how much
216 each predictor variable (each food item) contributes to the uncertainty or variability of
217 prediction (Shade and Jayjock, 1997).

218

219 2.4 Cohort Characteristics

220 A description of the characteristics of the study population is shown in Table 2. 43 % of
221mothers had university studies and 25 % had more than 12 years of education. Almost 75 % of
222the mothers were between 30 and 39 years old and 15 % were actively smoking during
223pregnancy. Regarding water consumption, most of the mothers drink bottled water (70 %) and
224most of them never eat organic products (56 %). Almost 50% of our cohort eats fast-food once a
225week and 70 % of them eat canned food between 1 and 3 times per week. This data can be
226directly related to the cohort's complexion (around 50 % of the pregnant mothers were
227overweight, and 15 % of them were obese).

228

229 2.5 Tissue dosimetry model (PBPK)

230A previously developed and validated adult PBPK model of BPA (Sharma et al., 2016 b,
231unpublished) and of DEHP (Sharma et al., 2016 c, unpublished) was adapted for the pregnancy-
232PBPK model and was used to estimate internal dosimetry of mothers and fetuses for the present
233cohort study. The basic structure of adult human PBPK model (which included plasma, liver,
234kidneys, filtrate, fat, brain, gonads and a rest of the body compartment for the remaining tissues)
235(Figure 1), has been adapted for pregnant women model. In addition, compartments of placenta
236and fetus were considered as a sub-model in order to predict the internal dosimetry for the fetus.
237It was subcategorized again into liver, brain, and plasma (Figure 1). The physiological and
238chemical-specific parameters were adapted from the adult human model and modified for the
239fetuses and mothers as a function of the gestational period. The metabolism capacity in the fetus
240was scaled from the adult data. The source of exposure to fetuses was through free fraction of
241chemicals into mothers placenta, considering that fetuses exposure is directly related to
242mother's exposure. The placental-fetal unit assumes a bidirectional transfer process describing
243chemical transfer between mother's placenta to fetus plasma and fetus plasma to the mother. A
244detailed description of standard and pregnancy specific model equations are provided in
245supplementary material (Annex-I). All physiological parameters were considered as a function

246of gestational day and model equations were adapted from different literature sources and are
247provided in Annex-I. Metabolic kinetic parameters namely V_{max} (maximum rate of reaction)
248and K_m (affinity of the substrate for the enzyme), for mothers and fetuses, were taken from in-
249vitro studies and were scaled to in-vivo. The chemical-specific parameters are also provided in
250supplementary material (Annex-I).

251 PBPK model inputs were the outputs of the Monte-Carlo simulation used previously for the
252exposure assessment. We considered three total dietary intake scenarios of BPA and DEHP: 5th
253percentile, mean and 95th percentile. In addition, a biologically active metabolite of DEHP,
254MEHP was considered as relevant internal exposure chemical and was used as an input in the
255PBPK simulation model to estimate fetus exposure. DEHP is rapidly metabolized into MEHP
256(Latini, 2005) and normally stay in the systemic circulation of mother's body and pass to the
257fetuses.

258

259 **3. Results and Discussion**

260 *3.1 BPA and DEHP total dietary intake and food categories contribution*

261 The contribution of each food item to the total dietary intake for the Tarragona population
262cohort was assessed in a probabilistic way using a Monte-Carlo simulation. Figure 2,
263summarizes the food categories contributing to the total dietary intake of BPA (Figure 2, A.1)
264and DEHP (Figure 2, A.2)

265 Regarding BPA (Figure 2, A.1), the total dietary intake mean value was 0.72 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{day}$
266(0.28 and 1.42 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{day}$ for 5th and 95th percentile, respectively). The variable showing the
267greatest contribution to the total dietary intake mean value was "fruits and vegetables" with 49
268%, followed by "meat and meat products" with 26 %. The contribution of the remaining food
269categories were 8 %, 5 %, 4 %, 4 %, 2 % and 2 % corresponding to "fish and other seafood",
270"water consumption" (bottled water and tap water were considered, but only bottled water
271added risk of exposure to BPA), "grain and grain-base products", "milk and dairy products",
272"ready to eat (including canned food)" and "legumes", respectively.

273 The high contribution (49 %) of “fruits and vegetables” to the total dietary intake was due to
274the high consumption of this food item (an average of 21.1 servings per week), typical of a
275Mediterranean diet. The concentration of BPA in fruits and vegetables was not excessively high
276compared with other food items, with an average concentration of 9.92 µg/kg, although there
277was a maximum value of 116 µg/kg due to canned fruits and vegetables. It should be noted that
278fruits and vegetables are also packaged in plastic and in these cases, migration of BPA to the
279products occurs (Lakind and Naiman, 2010). The next major contributor to the total dietary
280intake was “meat and meat products” with a contribution of 26 % and an average concentration
281of BPA of 36.9 µg/kg and a maximum value of 395 µg/kg (canned). In this case, unlike the
282group of fruits and vegetables, although the frequency of consumption is lower, the levels of
283BPA in this category are higher.

284 EFSA (2015) published its comprehensive re-evaluation of BPA exposure and toxicity, in
285January 2015 it established a TDI of 4 µg/kg bw/day for BPA. In the present study, although the
286maximum value estimated was 4.40 µg/kg bw/day, 95% of the population were under 1.41
287µg/kg bw/day. In addition, the present study data matches with the established values, which
288FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization)/WHO set during the last expert meeting in order to
289review the toxicological and health aspects of BPA. For adults, the highest exposure estimates
290did not exceed 1.4 µg/kg bw per day at the mean and 4.2 µg/kg bw/day at the 95th percentile
291(FAO/WHO, 2010).

292 Regarding DEHP, the total dietary intake mean value for our cohort was 1.00 µg/kg bw/day
293(0.41 µg/kg bw/day and 2.01 µg/kg bw/day for 5th and 95th percentile, respectively) (Figure 2,
294A.2). The maximum contribution to this exposure comes from “milk and dairy products” with
29556 %, followed by “ready to eat (including canned food)” with 30 %. The other food items
296“grain and grain-base products”, “meat and meat products”, “fruits and vegetables”, “fish and
297other seafood” and “water consumption” (bottled water and tap water were considered)
298contributed to 6 %, 4 %, 3 %, 1 %, and 1 %, respectively.

299 On the one hand, the high contribution (56 %) of “milk and dairy products” category to the
300total dietary intake of DEHP in the present study is due to the high DEHP levels in milk and

301dairy products (with a mean and maximum of 126 and 173 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, respectively) in comparison
302to other categories. DEHP contamination of milk and dairy products occurs in several stages:
303contaminated DEHP feed, mechanical milking process, and migration from packaging material
304used in milk and dairy products (Fierens et al., 2013). Milk and dairy products were the second
305most consumed food item during pregnancy (an average of 6.86 servings per week), which can
306also be related to the general recommendation for a pregnant woman of maintaining optimal
307levels of calcium in the body in order to prevent adverse gestational outcomes (WHO, 2013).
308Also, the high concentration of DEHP in this food group is due to lipophilic nature of
309phthalates; and for this reason, it is assumed that high-fat foods contain more phthalates than
310low-fat food products (Fierens et al., 2013). Various authors (Page and Lacroix, 1989; Sharman
311et al., 1994) reported that there is a positive relationship between the fat content of a dairy
312product and the DEHP content in that product. The second most contributed food item to the
313total dietary intake of DEHP was ready to eat food (30 %). It has been found a strong
314correlation between fast food intake and phthalates exposure but not with BPA exposure. This
315evidence coincides with another study from the USA, in which they observe the same evidence
316of a positive dose-response relationship between fast food intake and DEHP exposure but not
317for BPA (Zota et al., 2016).

318 The EFSA and the ECHA established the total daily intake for DEHP to 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw/day
319(EFSA, 2015; ECHA, 2010). In this study, both, the maximum (11.4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw/day) and the 95th
320percentile (2.01 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw/day) were far below this threshold.

321 Finally, the concentration of BPA and DEHP in bottle water was found in the literature data.
322However, in tap water, only levels of DEHP was found (Table 1). The presence of DEHP in tap
323water is due to leaching from PVC tubes and others materials from the pipes (Santana et al.,
3242014).

325

326 3.2 *Dietary exposure compared to other countries*

327 Table 3 shows the BPA and DEHP total dietary intake in adult populations in different
328 countries. All data from the studies in Table 3 were experimentally analyzed in different food
329 items.

330 Regarding BPA, it can be observed that the mean daily intake of it in the Tarragona cohort
331 (Spain) was in the same order of magnitude as data presented for the Spanish cohort in EFSA
332 report (EFSA b) (EFSA, 2013) and it was slightly below the European mean dietary intake of
333 previous EFSA report (EFSA, 2006). Total dietary intake of BPA in Tarragona was also in the
334 same order of magnitude as in Taiwan (Chen et al., 2016). However, data from countries such as
335 France (Bemrah et al., 2014), Belgium (Geens et al., 2010), and USA (Lorber et al., 2015) were
336 one order of magnitude lower; whereas, countries such as New Zealand (Thomson and Grounds,
337 2005), and Norway (Sakhi et al., 2014) were two orders of magnitude lower than the Tarragona
338 study.

339 Regarding DEHP, it can be observed that the mean daily intake in the Tarragona cohort
340 (Spain) was in the same order of magnitude as data presented from other European studies such
341 as Belgium (Sioen et al., 2012), France (Martine et al., 2013) and Switzerland (Dickson-
342 Spillmann et al., 2009). The present study estimations were in the same order of magnitude as
343 Norway (Sakhi et al., 2014), USA (Schechter et al., 2013), Germany (Fromme et al., 2007) and
344 China (Sui et al., 2014). However, DEHP exposure in countries like Cambodia (Cheng et al.,
345 2013) and Germany (Heinemeyer et al., 2013) were presented one order of magnitude higher
346 than the Tarragona's results.

347 It should be noted that dietary preference and food sources in different regions might lead to
348 variability of the estimated daily intakes of EDs. In addition, it is important to mention that not
349 all studies have considered exactly the same items and that could lead to differences in results.
350 Despite this, estimated daily dietary exposure to DEHP and BPA in our study is comparable
351 with other studies worldwide (Table 3).

352

353 3.3 *Internal dosimetry*

354 The chemicals' dose inputs considered to run the PBPK, were probabilistically estimated by
355 Monte-Carlo simulation (section 3.1). From probabilistic distribution, three total dietary intake
356 reference scenarios were selected for BPA and DEHP: the 5th percentile, the mean and the 95th
357 percentile. The outputs generated after running the model were selected considering the
358 metabolites generated, their toxicity, gestational period and ability to reach the fetus. For this
359 reason, only free BPA and MEHP (a metabolite of DEHP) were considered.

360 The simulation was performed for pregnant women and fetus for 24 hours during the 24th
361 gestational week. This period was selected because at this time fetus organs are more developed
362 and able to incorporate right biological process. This helps us to explain the difference in
363 metabolic processes in mothers and fetuses. Normally, at the early stage of pregnancy, for both
364 BPA and MEHP, fetus plasma concentration level is higher due to low or no metabolic
365 activities in the fetus (Gauderat et al., 2016; Latini et al., 2003). In order to understand the
366 elimination profile of the chemicals (BPA and MEHP) in the body, single dose simulation for
367 all three exposure scenarios (5th percentile; mean; 95th percentile) was simulated. Time versus
368 plasma concentration (for mothers and fetuses) of BPA and MEHP are shown in Figure 3 and 4,
369 respectively. Due to the fast absorption properties of BPA and DEHP, simulated concentration
370 curves show a sharp peak concentration observed within 1 hour of intake. Both, BPA and
371 MEHP are fast elimination chemicals, with a half-life of fewer than 2 hours and complete
372 elimination within 24 hours in adult (mother). The elimination of BPA and MEHP in the fetuses
373 is slower than mothers as the fetal metabolic activity is lower comparing mother's metabolism.
374 In general, it was observed that BPA and MEHP stay longer in the fetal body, which may cause
375 higher risk to fetuses compare with the mothers even for lower exposure scenario (Figure 3 and
376 4). Similar results have been observed by Sharma et al., (2016 b, c, unpublished) for BPA and
377 MEHP, respectively. In reality, the oral exposure has multiple intakes and in that case, the
378 residence time of the chemical in the human body increases. However, absorption and
379 elimination profile of chemical after three intakes have little or no effect. Figure 5 summarizes
380 the levels concentration of BPA in plasma in mothers and fetuses considering three oral intakes.

381 To simulate three doses scenario, the single intake was divided into three with 8 hours of
382 interval. The area under the curve for each day has increased significantly with higher residence
383 time but lower peak compares to one oral dose scenario. In multiple dose scenarios, absorption
384 peak concentration for each intake time and the half-life of elimination are similar to single dose
385 scenario with 1 hour for the peak and less than 2 hours for the half-life. However, in multiple
386 dose scenarios, as each intake is lower than single-dose intake, peak concentrations for the
387 corresponding intake are lower. For example, the peak concentration of BPA (95th percentile)
388 for mothers and fetuses considering only one dose were 0.047 µg/L and 0.039 µg/L,
389 respectively and considering multiple doses, were 0.015 µg/L (95th percentile) and 0.018 µg/L
390 (95th percentile) for mothers and fetuses, respectively; this peaks concentrations were around 1/3
391 of the value for one dose. Although, in the case of fetus, the peak concentration was slightly
392 more than 1/3 due to his low metabolic capacity. In the case of MEHP, the profile was the same
393 as the BPA. For only one dose the plasma concentration peak was 11 µg/L (P95) in the mothers
394 and 9 µg/L (P95) in the fetuses and considering three doses, it was obtained values that were the
395 third part of the previous ones mentioned. It was observed that the concentration peaks of
396 DEHP in plasma were higher compared with BPA. However, it should be noted that the
397 probabilistic total dietary intake of DEHP obtained by Monte-Carlo was higher than the total
398 dietary intake obtained for BPA.

399 Despite their short biological half-lives, exposure is prevalent and detectable in blood matrix at
400 any time. Mothers are able to decrease much more the basal levels of these chemicals compared
401 to the fetuses due to her metabolic activity. For that reason, fetuses are always subject to a risk
402 of constant exposure. The results of the present study were not comparable with biomonitoring
403 studies for multiple reasons. Firstly, in the present case study, only oral exposure was estimated
404 whereas, in reality, both BPA and DEHP have multi-route exposure with significant
405 contribution from coming from dermal exposure (Myridakis et al., 2016). Secondly, both BPA
406 and DEHP show high variability in their internal dosimetry with no steady state concentration,
407 which makes the timing of biomonitoring sampling very relevant. Which means, the
408 concentration levels of the EDs obtained from plasma are subject to different conditions such as

409the diet of each patient, the time of sampling (it will not be the same concentration if it is
410collected after longer period without any exposure or closer to peak hour of exposure) and the
411routes of exposure (oral vs dermal).

412

413 **4. Conclusions**

414 The aim of this study was to estimate the prenatal exposure to EDs (BPA and DEHP)
415through the dietary intake of pregnant women using the interview-based method, in order to
416improve the knowledge about the risks that they pose to prenatal health. To assess the early
417exposure, integrated external and internal dosimetry estimate was performed.

418 Canned fruits and vegetables followed by canned meat and meat products were the major
419contributors to the dietary exposure to BPA in pregnant women population in Tarragona
420(Spain). For DEHP, milk and dairy products followed by ready to eat food (included canned
421dinners) were the most important contributors to the estimated dietary exposure. In spite of
422dietary variation and resulting differences in exposure, the total dietary intake estimate for BPA
423and DEHP was considerably lower than their respective current TDI values established by
424EFSA (4 and 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw/day, respectively) (EFSA, 2015). Internal dosimetry simulations
425carried out in this study suggest that free BPA and MEHP plasma concentrations in women
426were characterized by transient peaks (associated with meals). In contrast, fetal exposure was
427characterized by a low but sustained basal BPA and MEHP concentration due to a lack of
428metabolic activity in the fetus.

429 The ongoing research is to validate the PBPK model with biological samples from this
430cohort and demonstrate that this methodology allows the determination of BPA and MEHP for
431monitoring in plasma and urine biological matrices and the PBPK model can predict the
432prenatal exposure of the child/fetus to EDs.

433 Finally, the health implications of this fetal exposure to BPA and MEHP should be
434addressed because they are associated with infertility issues and reproductive development of

435the fetus. Therefore, a strategy to reduce their exposure is to regulate their production and
436restrict their use in articles specially meant for childcare and pregnant women.

437

438 **5. Acknowledgement**

439 We would like to thank all pregnant women who participate in this study. The research
440leading to these results has received funding from the European Community's Seventh
441Framework Programme (FP7/2007-2013) under Grant Agreement No. 603946-2 (HEALS
442project). J. Rovira receives funds from Health Department of Catalonia Government, through
443"Pla Estratègic de Recerca i Innovació en salut" (PERIS 2016-2020) fellowship.

444

445**References**

446Arbuckle, T.E., Davis, K., Boylan, K., Fisher, M., Fu, J., 2016. Processed data for CHMS 2007-
447 2009: Bisphenol A, phthalates and lead and learning and behavioral problems in Canadian
448 children 6-19 years of age. *Data Br.* 8, 784–802. doi:10.1016/j.dib.2016.06.017

449Bemrah, N., Jean, J., Rivière, G., Sanaa, M., Leconte, S., Bachelot, M., Deceuninck, Y., Bizec,
450 B. Le, Dauchy, X., Roudot, A.C., Camel, V., Grob, K., Feidt, C., Picard-Hagen, N., Badot,
451 P.M., Foures, F., Leblanc, J.C., 2014. Assessment of dietary exposure to bisphenol A in
452 the French population with a special focus on risk characterisation for pregnant French
453 women. *Food Chem. Toxicol.* 72, 90–97. doi:10.1016/j.fct.2014.07.005

454Casas, L., Fernández, M.F., Llop, S., Guxens, M., Ballester, F., Olea, N., Irurzun, M.B.,
455 Rodríguez, L.S.M., Riaño, I., Tardón, A., Vrijheid, M., Calafat, A.M., Sunyer, J., 2011.
456 Urinary concentrations of phthalates and phenols in a population of Spanish pregnant
457 women and children. *Environ. Int.* 37, 858–866. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2011.02.012

458Chen, W.Y., Shen, Y.P., Chen, S.C., 2016. Assessing bisphenol A (BPA) exposure risk from
459 long-term dietary intakes in Taiwan. *Sci. Total Environ.* 543, 140–146.
460 doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.11.029

461Cheng, Z., Wang, H.-S., Du, J., Sthiannopkao, S., Xing, G.-H., Kim, K.-W., Yasin, M.S.M.,
462 Hashim, J.H., Wong, M.-H., 2013. Dietary exposure and risk assessment of mercury via
463 total diet study in Cambodia. *Environ. Res.* 92, 143–9.
464 doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2013.02.025

465Dapcich, V., Salvador, G., Ribas, L., Pérez, C., Aranceta, J., 2004. Consejos para una
466 alimentación saludable de la Sociedad Española de Nutrición Comunitaria (SENC). Ed
467 Spanish Soc. Community Nutr. 105.

468Das, M.T., Ghosh, P., Thakur, I.S., 2014. Intake estimates of phthalate esters for South Delhi
469 population based on exposure media assessment. *Environ. Pollut.* 189, 118–125.

- 470 doi:10.1016/j.envpol.2014.02.021
- 471 Davis, B.J., Maronpot, R.R., Heindel, J.J., 1994. Di (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate suppresses
472 estradiol and ovulation in cycling rats. *Toxicol. Appl. Pharmacol.* 128, 216–23.
473 doi:10.1006/taap.1994.1200
- 474 De Cock, M., de Boer, M.R., Lamoree, M., Legler, J., van de Bor, M., 2014. First year growth
475 in relation to prenatal exposure to endocrine disruptors - A dutch prospective cohort study.
476 *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 11, 7001–7021. doi:10.3390/ijerph110707001
- 477 De Coensel, N., David, F., Sandra, P., 2009. Study on the migration of bisphenol-A from baby
478 bottles by stir bar sorptive extraction thermal desorption-capillary GC-MS. *J. Sep. Sci.* 32,
479 3829–3836. doi:10.1002/jssc.200900349
- 480 Dickson-Spillmann, M., Siegrist, M., Keller, C., Wormuth, M., 2009. Phthalate exposure
481 through food and consumers' risk perception of chemicals in food. *Risk Anal.* 29, 1170–
482 1181. doi:10.1111/j.1539-6924.2009.01233.x
- 483 ECHA, 2010. Review of new available information for Bis (2-Ethylhexyl) Phthalate (DEHP).
484 Evaluation of new scientific evidence concerning the restrictions contained in Annex XVII
485 to Regulation (Ec) No 1907/2006 (Reach). ECHA 2006, 1–24.
- 486 EFSA, 2015. Scientific Opinion on the risks to public health related to the presence of bisphenol
487 A (BPA) in foodstuffs: Executive summary. *EFSA J.* 13, 1–621.
488 doi:doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2015.3978
- 489 EFSA, 2013. Draft Scientific Opinion on the risks to public health related to the presence of
490 bisphenol A (BPA) in foodstuffs– Part: exposure assessment. *EFSA J.* 314. doi:No
491 EFSA-Q-2012-00423
- 492 EFSA, 2006. Opinion of the Scientific Panel on Food Additives, Flavourings, Processing Aids
493 and Materials in Contact with Food on a request from the Commission related to Maltitol
494 Syrup E 965 (ii) new production process. Change of specification Question number E.
495 *EFSA J.* 428, 75. doi:http://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/science/afc/afc_opinions.html
- 496 European-Parliament, 2011. Commission Directive 2011/8/EU. *Off. J. Eur. Communities* 29–32.
- 497 Fàbrega, F., Kumar, V., Schuhmacher, M., Domingo, J.L., Nadal, M., 2014. PBPK modeling for
498 PFOS and PFOA: Validation with human experimental data. *Toxicology Letters* 230(2),
499 224-251.
- 500 Fàbrega, F., Kumar, V., Schuhmacher, M., Domingo, J.L., Nadal, M., 2015. Physiologically
501 based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) modeling of perfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) in the
502 human body, *Archives of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology* 97(6), 814-827.
- 503 Fàbrega, F., Nadal, M., Schuhmacher, M., Domingo, J.L., Kumar, V., 2016. Influence of the
504 uncertainty in the validation of PBPK models: A case-study for PFOS and PFOA. *Regul.*
505 *Toxicol. Pharmacol.* 77, 230–239. doi:10.1016/j.yrtph.2016.03.009
- 506 FAO/WHO, 2010. Joint FAO / WHO Expert meeting to review toxicological and health aspects
507 of Bisphenol A Canada , October 2010 Call for data. WHO 1–2.
- 508 Fierens, T., Van Holderbeke, M., Willems, H., De Henauw, S., Sioen, I., 2013. Transfer of eight
509 phthalates through the milk chain — A case study. *Environ. Int.* 51, 1–7.
510 doi:10.1016/j.envint.2012.10.002

- 511 Fromme, H., Gruber, L., Schlummer, M., Wolz, G., Böhmer, S., Angerer, J., Mayer, R., Liebl,
512 B., Bolte, G., 2007. Intake of phthalates and di (2-ethylhexyl) adipate: Results of the
513 Integrated Exposure Assessment Survey based on duplicate diet samples and
514 biomonitoring data. *Environ. Int.* 33, 1012–1020. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2007.05.006
- 515 Gauderat, G., Picard-Hagen, N., Toutain, P.L., Corbel, T., Viguié, C., Puel, S., Lacroix, M.Z.,
516 Mindeguia, P., Bousquet-Melou, A., Gayraud, V., 2016. Bisphenol A glucuronide
517 deconjugation is a determining factor of fetal exposure to bisphenol A. *Environ. Int.* 86,
518 52–59. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2015.10.006
- 519 Geens, T., Aerts, D., Berthot, C., Bourguignon, J.P., Goeyens, L., Lecomte, P., Maghuin-
520 Rogister, G., Pironnet, A.M., Pussemier, L., Scippo, M.L., Van Loco, J., Covaci, A., 2012.
521 A review of dietary and non-dietary exposure to bisphenol-A. *Food Chem. Toxicol.*
522 doi:10.1016/j.fct.2012.07.059
- 523 Geens, T., Apelbaum, T.Z., Goeyens, L., Neels, H., Covaci, A., 2010. Intake of bisphenol A
524 from canned beverages and foods on the Belgian market. *Food Addit. Contam. Part A.*
525 *Chem. Anal. Control. Expo. Risk Assess.* 27, 1627–37.
526 doi:10.1080/19440049.2010.508183
- 527 Genuis, S.J., Beeson, S., Lobo, R. a., Birkholz, D., 2012. Human Elimination of Phthalate
528 Compounds: Blood, Urine, and Sweat (BUS) Study. *Sci. World J.* 2012, 1–10.
529 doi:10.1100/2012/615068
- 530 Giulivo, M., Lopez, M., Alda, D., Capri, E., Barceló, D., 2016. Human exposure to endocrine
531 disrupting compounds: Their role in reproductive systems , metabolic syndrome and
532 breast cancer . A review. *Environ. Res.* 151, 251–264. doi:10.1016/j.envres.2016.07.011
- 533 Gobas, F., Otton, V., Tupper-Ring, L., Crawford, M., Clark, K., Ikonou, M., 2016. Chemical
534 activity-based environmental risk analysis of the plasticizer p di-ethylhexyl phthalate and
535 its main metabolite mono-ethylhexyl phthalate. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 31.
536 doi:10.1002/etc.3689
- 537 Gramec Skledar, D., Peterlin Mašič, L., 2016. Bisphenol A and its analogs: Do their metabolites
538 have endocrine activity? *Environ. Toxicol. Pharmacol.* 47, 182–199.
539 doi:10.1016/j.etap.2016.09.014
- 540 Hanioka, N., Naito, T., Narimatsu, S., 2008. Human UDP-glucuronosyltransferase isoforms
541 involved in bisphenol A glucuronidation. *Chemosphere* 74, 33–36.
542 doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2008.09.053
- 543 Hanson, M.A., Gluckman, P.D., 2011. Developmental origins of health and disease: Moving
544 from biological concepts to interventions and policy. *Int. J. Gynecol. Obstet.* 115, S3–S5.
545 doi:10.1016/S0020-7292(11)60003-9
- 546 Hartle, J.C., Navas-Acien, A., Lawrence, R.S., 2016. The consumption of canned food and
547 beverages and urinary Bisphenol A concentrations in NHANES 2003-2008. *Environ. Res.*
548 150, 375–382. doi:10.1016/j.envres.2016.06.008
- 549 Heinemeyer, G., Sommerfeld, C., Springer, A., Heiland, A., Lindtner, O., Greiner, M., Heuer,
550 T., Krems, C., Conrad, A., 2013. Estimation of dietary intake of bis(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate
551 (DEHP) by consumption of food in the German population. *Int. J. Hyg. Environ. Health*
552 216, 472–480. doi:10.1016/j.ijheh.2013.01.001
- 553 Hughes, I.A., Martin, H., Jaaskelainen, J., 2006. Genetic mechanisms of fetal male

- 554 undermasculinization: A background to the role of endocrine disruptors. *Int. J. Environ.*
555 *Res. Public Heal.* 100, 44–49. doi:10.1016/j.envres.2005.07.001
- 556Kim, Y.H., Kim, C.S., Park, S., Han, S.Y., Pyo, M.Y., Yang, M., 2003. Gender differences in
557 the levels of bisphenol A metabolites in urine. *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.* 312,
558 441–448. doi:10.1016/j.bbrc.2003.10.135
- 559Lakind, J.S., Naiman, D.Q., 2010. Daily intake of bisphenol A and potential sources of
560 exposure: 2005-2006 National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey. *J. Expo. Sci.*
561 *Environ. Epidemiol.* 21, 272–9. doi:10.1038/jes.2010.9
- 562Latini, G., 2005. Monitoring phthalate exposure in humans. *Clin. Chim. Acta* 361, 20–29.
563 doi:10.1016/j.cccn.2005.05.003
- 564Latini, G., De Felice, C., Presta, G., Del Vecchio, A., Paris, I., Ruggieri, F., Mazzeo, P., 2003.
565 Exposure to Di(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate in humans during pregnancy: A preliminary report.
566 *Biol. Neonate* 83, 22–24. doi:10.1159/000067012
- 567Lorber, M., Schecter, A., Paepke, O., Shropshire, W., Christensen, K., Birnbaum, L., 2015.
568 Exposure assessment of adult intake of bisphenol A (BPA) with emphasis on canned food
569 dietary exposures. *Environ. Int.* 77, 55–62. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2015.01.008
- 570Lovekamp-Swan, T., Davis, B.J., 2003. Mechanisms of phthalate ester toxicity in the female
571 reproductive system. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 111, 139–145. doi:10.1289/ehp.5658
- 572Maffini, M. V., Rubin, B.S., Sonnenschein, C., Soto, A.M., 2006. Endocrine disruptors and
573 reproductive health: The case of bisphenol-A. *Mol. Cell. Endocrinol.* 254–255, 179–186.
574 doi:10.1016/j.mce.2006.04.033
- 575Mallozzi, M., Bordi, G., Garo, C., Caserta, D., 2016. Review The Effect of Maternal Exposure
576 to Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals on Fetal and Neonatal Development: A Review on the
577 Major Concerns. *Wiley Period. Inc.* 19. doi:10.1002/bdrc.21137
- 578Mari, M., Nadal, M., Schuhmacher, M., Domingo, J.L., 2009. Exposure to heavy metals and
579 PCDD/Fs by the population living in the vicinity of a hazardous waste landfill in
580 Catalonia, Spain: Health risk assessment. *Environ. Int.* 35, 1034–1039.
581 doi:10.1016/j.envint.2009.05.004
- 582Martine, B., Marie-Jeanne, T., Cendrine, D., Fabrice, A., Marc, C., 2013. Assessment of adult
583 human exposure to phthalate esters in the urban centre of paris (France). *Bull. Environ.*
584 *Contam. Toxicol.* 90, 91–96. doi:10.1007/s00128-012-0859-5
- 585Matsui, S., 2008. Endocrine Disruptors. *Encycl. Toxicol.* 1259–1260.
586 doi:http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/B978-008045405-4.00402-X
- 587May, L.M., Gaborek, B., Pitrat, T., Peters, L., 2002. Derivation of risk based wipe surface
588 screening levels for industrial scenarios. *Sci. Total Environ.* 288, 65–80.
589 doi:10.1016/S0048-9697(01)01117-2
- 590Meeker, J., 2012. Exposure to environmental endocrine disruptors and child development. *Arch.*
591 *Pediatr. Adolesc.* 166, E1–E7. doi:10.1001/archpediatrics.2012.241.Exposure
- 592Myridakis, A., Chalkiadaki, G., Fotou, M., Kogevinas, M., Chatzi, L., Stephanou, E.G., 2016.
593 Exposure of Preschool-Age Greek Children (RHEA Cohort) to Bisphenol A, Parabens,
594 Phthalates, and Organophosphates. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 50, 932–941.

- 595 doi:10.1021/acs.est.5b03736
- 596Page, B.D., Lacroix, G.M., 1989. The occurrence of phthalate ester and di-2-ethylhexyl adipate
597 plasticizers in Canadian packaging and food sampled in 1985-1989: a survey. *Food Addit.*
598 *Contam.* 12, 129–151. doi:10.1080/02652039509374287
- 599Rezg, R., El-Fazaa, S., Gharbi, N., Mornagui, B., 2014. Bisphenol A and human chronic
600 diseases: Current evidences, possible mechanisms, and future perspectives. *Environ. Int.*
601 64, 83–90. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2013.12.007
- 602Rochester, J.R., 2013. Bisphenol A and human health: A review of the literature. *Reprod.*
603 *Toxicol.* 42, 132–155. doi:10.1016/j.reprotox.2013.08.008
- 604Rovira, J., Roig, N., Nadal, M., Schuhmacher, M., Domingo, J.L., 2016. Human health risks of
605 formaldehyde indoor levels: An issue of concern. *J. Environ. Sci. Heal. Part a-*
606 *Toxic/Hazardous Subst. Environ. Eng.* 51, 357–363. doi:10.1080/10934529.2015.1109411
- 607Sakhi, A.K., Lillegaard, I.T.L., Voorspoels, S., Carlsen, M.H., Løken, E.B., Brantsæter, A.L.,
608 Haugen, M., Meltzer, H.M., Thomsen, C., 2014. Concentrations of phthalates and
609 bisphenol A in Norwegian foods and beverages and estimated dietary exposure in adults.
610 *Environ. Int.* 73, 259–269. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2014.08.005
- 611Santana, J., Giraudi, C., Marengo, E., Robotti, E., Pires, S., Nunes, I., Gaspar, E.M., 2014.
612 Preliminary toxicological assessment of phthalate esters from drinking water consumed in
613 Portugal. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 21, 1380–1390. doi:10.1007/s11356-013-2020-3
- 614Schechter, A., Lorber, M., Guo, Y., Wu, Q., Yun, S.H., Kannan, K., Hommel, M., Imran, N.,
615 Hynan, L.S., Cheng, D., Colacino, J.A., Birnbaum, L.S., 2013. Phthalate concentrations
616 and dietary exposure from food purchased in New York state. *Environ. Health Perspect.*
617 121, 473–479. doi:10.1289/ehp.1206367
- 618Schuhmacher, M., Fàbrega, F., Kumar, V., García, F., Nadal, M., Domingo, J.L., 2014. A PBPK
619 model to estimate PCDD/F levels in adipose tissue: Comparison with experimental values
620 of residents near a hazardous waste incinerator. *Environ. Int.* 73, 150–157.
621 doi:10.1016/j.envint.2014.07.020
- 622Schuhmacher, M., Meneses, M., Xifr, A., Domingo, J.L., 2001. The use of Monte-Carlo
623 simulation techniques for risk assessment: study of a municipal waste incinerator.
624 *Chemosphere* 43, 787–799.
- 625Serra Majem, L., 2011. Objetivos nutricionales para la población española: consenso de la
626 Sociedad Española de Nutrición Comunitaria 2011. *Rev. española Nutr. comunitaria*
627 (Spanish J. community Nutr). 17, 178–199.
- 628Shade, W.D., Jayjock, M. a, 1997. Monte Carlo uncertainty analysis of a diffusion model for the
629 assessment of halogen gas exposure during dosing of brominators. *Am. Ind. Hyg. Assoc.*
630 *J.* 58, 418–24. doi:10.1080/15428119791012658
- 631Sharma, R.P., Schuhmacher, M., Kumar, V., 2016. Review on crosstalk and common
632 mechanisms of endocrine disruptors: Scaffolding to improve PBPK/PD model of EDC
633 mixture. *Environ. Int.* 14. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2016.09.016
- 634Sharman, M., Read, W. a, Castle, L., Gilbert, J., 1994. Levels of di (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate and
635 total phthalate esters in milk, cream, butter and cheese. *Food Addit. Contam.* 11, 375–385.
636 doi:10.1080/02652039409374236

- 637Sioen, I., Fierens, T., Van Holderbeke, M., Geerts, L., Bellemans, M., De Maeyer, M., Servaes,
638 K., Vanermen, G., Boon, P.E., De Henauw, S., 2012. Phthalates dietary exposure and food
639 sources for Belgian preschool children and adults. *Environ. Int.* 48, 102–108.
640 doi:10.1016/j.envint.2012.07.004
- 641Sui, H.-X., Zhang, L., Wu, P.-G., Song, Y., Yong, L., Yang, D.-J., Jiang, D.-G., Liu, Z.-P.,
642 2014. Concentration of di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP) in foods and its dietary
643 exposure in China. *Int. J. Hyg. Environ. Health* 217, 695–701.
644 doi:10.1016/j.ijheh.2014.02.006
- 645Sungur, Ş., Koroğlu, M., Özkan, A., 2014. Determination of bisphenol a migrating from canned
646 food and beverages in markets. *Food Chem.* 142, 87–91.
647 doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2013.07.034
- 648Tewar, S., Auinger, P., Braun, J.M., Lanphear, B., Yolton, K., Epstein, J.N., Ehrlich, S.,
649 Froehlich, T.E., 2016. Association of Bisphenol A exposure and Attention-Deficit /
650 Hyperactivity Disorder in a national sample of U.S. children. *Environ. Res.* 150, 112–
651 118. doi:10.1016/j.envres.2016.05.040
- 652Thomson, B.M., Grounds, P.R., 2005. Bisphenol A in canned foods in New Zealand: an
653 exposure assessment. *Food Addit. Contam.* 22, 65–72. doi:10.1080/02652030400027920
- 654Wang, Y., You, L., Zeng, Q., Sun, Y., Huang, Y., Wang, C., 2015. Phthalate exposure and
655 human semen quality: Results from an infertility clinic in China. *Environ. Res.* 142, 1–9.
656 doi:10.1016/j.envres.2015.06.010
- 657Welshons, W. V., Nagel, S.C., Vom Saal, F.S., 2006. Large effects from small exposures. III.
658 Endocrine mechanisms mediating effects of bisphenol A at levels of human exposure.
659 *Endocrinology* 147, 56–69. doi:10.1210/en.2005-1159
- 660WHO, 2013. Guideline: Calcium supplementation in pregnant women 1–35.
- 661WHO, 2012. Endocrine disruptors and child health. Possible developmental early effects of
662 endocrine disruptors on child health. World Health Organization, Geneva.
- 663Wormuth, M., Scheringer, M., Vollenweider, M., Hungerbühler, K., 2006. What are the sources
664 of exposure to eight frequently used phthalic acid esters in Europeans? *Risk Anal.* 26,
665 803–824. doi:10.1111/j.1539-6924.2006.00770.x
- 666Zota, A., Phillips, C., Mitro, S., 2016. Recent fast food consumption and Bisphenol A and
667 Phthalates exposure among the U.S. population in NHANES, 2003-2010. *Environ. Health*
668 *Perspect.* 124, 1521–1528. doi:http://dx.doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1510803
- 669
- 670

737	EFSA, 2015
738 DEHP concentration in	
739	C_{DEHP}
740	–
741	–
742	–
743	–
744 Grains and grain-based products	
745	–
746	$\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$
747	T
748	43 (18-61)
749	Sakhi et al., 2014
750 Fruits and vegetables	
751	–
752	$\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$
753	T
754	4.80 (0.05-9.50)
755	Sakhi et al., 2014
756 Meat and meat products	
757	–
758	$\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$
759	T
760	0 (0-64)
761	Sakhi et al., 2014
762 Fish and other seafood	
763	–
764	$\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$
765	T
766	0 (0-35)
767	Sakhi et al., 2014
768 Milk and dairy products	
769	–
770	$\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$
771	T
772	126 (19-173)
773	Sakhi et al., 2014
774 Ready to eat (including canned dinners)	
775	–
776	$\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$
777	T
778	136 (37-235)
779	Sakhi et al., 2014
780 Bottle water	
781	–
782	$\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$
783	LN
784	0.11 ± 0.05
785	Santana et al., 2014
786 Tap water	
787	–
788	$\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$
789	LN
790	0.16 ± 0.04
791	Santana et al., 2014
792 Food ration	
793	Fr
794	–
795	–
796	–
797	–
798 Grains and grain-based products	
799	–
800	kg/ration
801	U
802	0.05-0.07
803	Dapcich et al., 2004

804	
805	Fruits and vegetables
806	–
807	kg/ration
808	U
809	0.15-0.20
810	Dapcich et al., 2004
811	Legumes
812	–
813	kg/ration
814	U
815	0.06-0.08
816	Dapcich et al., 2004
817	Meat and meat products
818	–
819	kg/ration
820	U
821	0.10-0.13
822	Dapcich et al., 2004
823	Fish and other seafood
824	–
825	kg/ration
826	U
827	0.13-0.15
828	Dapcich et al., 2004
829	Milk and dairy products
830	–
831	kg/ration
832	U
833	0.26-0.34
834	Dapcich et al., 2004
835	Ready to eat (including canned dinners)
836	–
837	kg/ration
838	U
839	0.21-0.41
840	Dapcich et al., 2004
841	Food frequency
842	Ff
843	–
844	–
845	–
846	–
847	Grains and grain-based products
848	–
849	ration/week
850	LN
851	9.60 ± 3.57
852	Present study
853	Fruits and vegetables
854	–
855	ration/week
856	LN
857	21.1 ± 7.09
858	Present study
859	Legumes
860	–
861	ration/week
862	LN
863	1.80 ± 1.38
864	Present study
865	Meat and meat products
866	–
867	ration/week
868	LN

869		5.13 ± 2.81
870		Present study
871	Fish and other seafood	
872		–
873	ration/week	
874		LN
875		2.87 ± 1.74
876		Present study
877	Milk and dairy products	
878		–
879	ration/week	
880		LN
881		6.86 ± 4.59
882		Present study
883	Ready to eat (including canned dinners)	
884		–
885	ration/week	
886		LN
887		3.09 ± 1.82
888		Present study
889	Bottle Water	
890		–
891		L/day
892		LN
893		1.40 ± 0.67
894		Present study
895	Tap water	
896		–
897		L/day
898		LN
899		1.02 ± 0.50
900		Present study
901	Conversion factor	
902		–
903		day/week
904		–
905		7
906		
907	Bodyweight	
908		BW
909		kg
910		LN
911		65.5 ± 14.0
912		Present study
913	Mean, minimum, and maximum values were used for triangular distributions; Mean and standard deviation were used	
914	for log-normal; minimum, and maximum values for uniform distributions.	
915	Including canned and non-canned food.	
916	N= Log-normal; T= Triangular; U= Uniform; P= Punctual	
917		
918		
919		
920		
921		
922		
923		
924		

Table 2. Characteristics of the study population from Reus, Tarragona (Spain) (n=45).X		Characteristics of the study population	
	%		%
<i>Maternal age at delivery (years)</i>			
< 20	0	<i>Mother's diet</i>	
20-29	10	Omnivorous	96
30-39	73	Vegetarians	4
>40	17	Vegans	0
<i>Water consumption (liters)</i>			
<i>Twin pregnancy</i>	9	< 1	4
<i>Maternal pre-pregnancy BMI*</i>		1-2	85
Underweight (<19 kg/m ²)	11	>2	11
Normal (19-25 kg/m ²)	52	<i>Kind of water consumption</i>	
Overweight (>25 kg/m ²)	26	Tap water	16
Obese (>30 kg/m ²)	11	Bottled water	71
<i>Maternal pregnancy (20 GW) BMI*</i>			
Underweight (<19kg/m ²)	0	Both	13
Normal (19-25 kg/m ²)	41	<i>Eat in a plastic recipient (times/week)</i>	
Overweight (>25 kg/m ²)	44	Never	69
Obese (>30 kg/m ²)	15	1-3	4
<i>Maternal education</i>			
Primary	25	4-6	20
Secondary	32	> 6	7
University	43	<i>Eat canned food (times/ week)</i>	
<i>Social economic status</i>			
High level (> 35000 €/year)	25	Never	18
Median level (19000-35000 €/year)	57	1-3	71
Low level (< 9000-19000 €/year)	18	4-6	7
<i>Maternal country of origin</i>			
Spain	81	> 6	4
Other	19	<i>Eat Fast-food</i>	
<i>Marital Status</i>			
Living with the father	98	Never	29
Not living with the father	2	1 a week	47
<i>Maternal smoking</i>			
Never smoke	74	>1 a week	24
Not during pregnancy	11	<i>Eat organic products</i>	
During pregnancy	15	Never	56
		Hardly ever	18
		Sometimes	20
		Very often	7

*BMI= Body mass index

926**Table 3.** BPA and DEHP total dietary intake in adult populations found in the recent scientific
927literature.

	Year		Total dietary intake ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{day}$)	Reference
BPA				
		*		
Belgium	2004	Mean	0.015	Geens et al.,2010
Europe	2006	Mean	1.5	EFSA, 2006
France	2014	Mean range (P50 range; P95 range)	0.038-0.040 (0.033- 0.035; 0.077-0.0087)	Bemrah et al.,2014
New Zealand	2004	Mean (P50; P95)	0.008 (0.00; 0.041)	Thomson and Grounds, 2005
Norway	2014	Mean (P50; P95)	0.004 (0.003; 0.01)	Sakhi et al., 2014
Spain	2013	Mean (P95)	0.061 (0.099)	EFSA, 2013 ^a
Spain	2013	Mean (P95)	0.18 (0.33)	EFSA, 2013 ^b
Taiwan	2015	Mean (P50;P95)	0.64 (0.27;2.29)	Chen et al., 2016
USA	2010	Mean	0.012	Lorber et al., 2015
Tarragona, Spain	2016	Mean (P5; P95)	0.72 (0.28; 1.41)	Present study
DEHP				
Belgium	2012	Mean	1.59	Sioen et al., 2012
Cambodia	2016	Mean	11.67	Cheng et al., 2013
China	2011-2012	Mean (P97.5)	2.03 (3.64)	Sui et al., 2014
France	2008	Mean	1.46	Martine et al., 2013
Germany	2005	Mean (P50;P95)	2.5 (2.4;4.0)	Fromme et al., 2007
Germany	2005-2006	Mean (P95)	14 (28.5)	Heinemeyer et al., 2013
Norway	2014	Mean	0.42	Sakhi et al., 2014
Switzerland	2009	Mean	1.90	Dickson-Spillmann et al.,2009
USA	2013	Mean	0.67	Schechter et al., 2013
Tarragona, Spain	2016	Mean (P5; P95)	1.00 (0.41; 2.01)	Presentstudy

^aOnly foods specifically codified as canned in the dietary survey are assigned the corresponding occurrence level for BPA. ^bAny food category (at the lowest available level of food category classification) which has been codified as canned in at least one survey is always considered to be consumed as canned in all dietary surveys included in the Comprehensive Database.

* P5, P50, P95 and P97.5 are 5th, 50th, 95th and 97.5th percentile, respectively.

928

929

932**Figure 1.** Conceptual structure of pregnancy PBPK model for BPA and DEHP. Adapted PBPK
933model for pregnant women and fetus which included the body organs compartments for both.
934The compartments like placenta and fetus compartments were considered as a sub-model in
935order to predict the internal dosimetry for the fetus.

937

938 **Figure 2.** Food categories contribution to the total dietary intake of BPA (A.1) and DEHP (A.2)
 939 in $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{day}$. Results are given in mean (5th percentile; 95th percentile).

940

941

942 **Figure 3.** Time versus BPA plasma concentration for mothers and fetuses, considering different
 943 exposure scenarios (5th percentile; mean; 95th percentile) and only one food intake dose.

944

945

946 **Figure 4.** Time versus MEHP plasma concentration for mothers and fetuses, considering
 947 different exposure scenarios (5th percentile; median; 95th percentile) and only one food intake
 948 dose.

949

950

951 **Figure 5.** Time versus BPA plasma concentration for mothers and fetuses, considering different
 952 exposure scenarios (5th percentile; mean; 95th percentile) and three-food intake dose.